

Dithiocarbamates Residues Level in Selected Vegetables from Bukavu, Democratic Republic of Congo

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ABSTRACT

This study involved a survey on the use of dithiocarbamates in agriculture practices in Bukavu Region and the determination of their residues in vegetables (tomatoes and cabbages) from five main sites supplying Bukavu town with vegetables. A total of 75 vegetable samples from different fields were analysed using an HPLC-UV method developed by the Codex Committee on Pesticide Residues. Mancozeb, traded under the name Dithan-45 has been found to be widely used in Bukavu region especially in the protection tomato crops against pests. The analysis of extracts from tomato samples showed that they contained dithiocarbamate residues. The concentration of the residues in tomatoes varied (in mg.kg⁻¹) from no detectable (ND) to 1.33 for Kamanyola, ND to 1.87 for Nyangezi, 1.44 to 3.99 for Katana, 1.54 to 4.06 for Miti and ND to 4.65 for Mudaka samples. The average values \pm SD in mg.kg⁻¹ for the five study sites were 0.89 ± 0.35 , 1.31 ± 0.44 , 2.48 ± 1.02 , 2.71 ± 0.82 and 3.25 ± 1.25 respectively. The results further show that 24 % of the tomato samples had Mancozeb residue values above the MRLs of European Food Safety Authority and 33 % above the MRLs set by EPA, while 73 % were not good for consumption with regards to the maximum permitted level for dithiocarbamates in tomatoes (1 mg.kg⁻¹) in Germany. On the other hand, 83% of cabbage samples from all sites had no detectable Mancozeb residue levels and the rest had less than 0.1 mg.kg⁻¹.

Keywords: *Dithiocarbamates, residues, HPLC, vegetables, Bukavu.*

INTRODUCTION

Safe use of pesticides is an increasingly difficult problem for developing countries in Asia, Africa, and Latin America. The demand for higher agricultural production as a means of improving the population's standard of living has in particular aggravated the problem. This is because, the use of pesticides not only reduces the losses caused by various pests but also because their use facilitates large scale use of modern and progressive agriculture methods and improvement of the quality of farm products [1]. Although such usage is still low in developing countries in comparison to other regions of the world, there are trends towards mis- and overuse in many cropping systems.

The large scale use of pesticides, often very toxic or with other undesirable properties has brought so many problems. In the past four decades, researchers have been increasingly interested in the study of the acute toxicity of pesticides, their accumulation in the animal body, occurrence of residues in foodstuffs and their effect on the human body [2-4]. In particular, many questions have been raised about increasing levels of residues in foodstuffs,

implying great danger to the public health. Some of the compounds nowadays in use, such as organophosphorus, organosulfurs and organochlorines can be dangerous when mishandled or wrongly used, and there have been numerous accidents, in both human beings and animals, arising from negligence or forgetfulness, from the taking of calculated risks, or from failure to give or heed information and advice [1,5]. The breakdown products of these residues in the environment and on crops may be even more toxic than the parent compound itself.

In the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) as in most developing countries, pesticides have been used for many decades in agricultural practices, for instance in the cultivation of vegetables. Successive wars in the country since 1994 have disorganized the Regulatory Agencies so that, the Ministries responsible for Health, Environment, Nature Conservation and Agriculture are not able to control the use of pesticides in the whole country. The Congolese Office of Control (OCC) which is mandated to protect consumers against products that are not in

conformity with National Standards is not well facilitated and lacks the technical expertise. No monitoring is done in the sense of assessing the daily intake of pesticides in different foods. According to the Head of the provincial division of Environment and Natural Resources of Sud-Kivu, DRC is a signatory to many protocols, international regulations and Acts dealing with environment and pesticides, but has not yet initiated policies for controlling and assessing pesticides in the environment and in human and animal food and feed.

Tomatoes and cabbages are highly consumed in DRC as cooked vegetables and condiments as well as raw salads. These two crops are among plants which are seriously attacked by diseases such as tomato scab caused by microscopic mushrooms, and pests. Thus Farmers resort to different techniques of controlling pests and diseases among which is the application of pesticides. The most commonly used pesticides in Bukavu region are Dithianes which have dithiocarbamates as the active compounds and are marketed under the trade name of “Mancozeb” that contains more than 500g of dithiocarbamate per kilogram of the commercial powder. However some reliable data indicate that there are adverse consequences from the use of dithiocarbamates. Dithiocarbamates are responsible for some congenital anomalies, they are carcinogenic, teratogenic and mutagenic [6]. They affect cardiovascular, respiratory, gastrointestinal systems, blood and metabolism [7]. Despite the wide use of these Dithiocarbamates in Bukavu region of the DRC, there is no data on their residue levels in the crops that can be used by regulatory agencies to take informed decisions.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Description of the study area

Bukavu (Latitude: 2°30' S ; Longitude: 28°50' E) is the main town of Sud-Kivu in the Eastern part of DR C as shown in Figure 1, with a population of about 500 000 inhabitants. The study was conducted in five administrative entities supplying Bukavu town with tomatoes and cabbages:

- Kamanyola: 32.5 km south of Bukavu (Latitude: 2°45' S ; Longitude: 28°59' E),
- Katana: 25 km north of Bukavu (Latitude: 2°16' S ; Longitude: 28°47' E),
- Miti: 19.1 km north of Bukavu (Latitude: 2°20' S ; Longitude: 28°47' E),
- Mudaka: 16.2 km north of Bukavu (Latitude: 2°23' S ; Longitude: 28°47' E) and
- Nyangezi: 17.3 km south of Bukavu (Latitude: 2°39' S ; Longitude: 28°53' E).

For each site, nine samples from different fields of tomatoes and six samples of cabbages from different fields were harvested.

Survey on use of dithiocarbamates in Bukavu region

The survey was conducted by administering questionnaires, supplemented by professional interviews. Sixty farmers distributed over the five sites were interviewed.

Sample collection and preservation

On basis of responses from questionnaires, 9 fields were selected per site for tomato sampling and 6 fields for cabbage sampling. Mature tomatoes and cabbages were harvested directly from the fields for analysis. In each field three tomatoes or cabbages were taken diagonally (two in the extremities and one in the middle), for a good representative sampling.

Three tomatoes or three cabbages from the same fields made up one sample. Tomatoes and cabbages samples were collected in

plastic boxes, kept in cool boxes, and immediately brought to the laboratory of “Pharmacie et Gallénique” at “ Université Officielle de Bukavu” (U.O.B.) for extraction. The extraction was done on fresh samples to avoid the loss of dithiocarbamates due to drying. The extracts were preserved in cool boxes prior to analysis which was done at Makerere University, Uganda.

Figure 1: Bukavu city, DRC

Sample extraction and analysis for dithiocarbamate residues

The extraction, and the analysis was carried out at “Pharmacie et Galénique” laboratory Bukavu, DRC. and the Pesticide Residue laboratory Department of Chemistry, Makerere University, Uganda, respectively. Samples were cut into small peaces and mixed before weighing to make a good representative sample. Nine top most leaves of three cabbages and the outer pieces of three fresh tomatoes from each sampling field were cut into smaller pieces before weighing so that the entire sample was covered by the extraction liquid. To avoid the loss of dithiocarbamates (DTCs), samples were not ground to paste [8, 9].

Analytical procedure

The method used to determine the DTCs Residues was based on that suggested by Codex Committee on Pesticide Residues, Document reference CX/PR 07/39/6 Add.1, combined with that of Gustafsson, both adapted to our context and conditions [10,11]. The procedure can be summarized into three steps:

1°. Extraction:

For tomato samples: an aliquot (50g) of the cut sample extracted immediately as follow: 100ml of EDTA solution (pH 9.5-9.6) and 0.5g of L-cysteine were added to the sample contained in a glass flask of 250 ml, the mixture was shaken for 5 min in the closed glass flask. Then after the mixture was centrifuged (Centrifuge model ECCO D 1000) for 10 min at 1,700 rpm before filtering on sintered glass funnel. The bottle and the filter was rinsed with 10 ml of the EDTA solution, and combined into the extracts. 5 mL of 0.41 mol. L⁻¹ tetrabutylammonium hydrogen sulphate and 10g of sodium chloride was added into the extracts while stirring. The pH of the extracts was cautiously adjusted to 7.0 with 2 mol. L⁻¹ hydrochloric acid.

For cabbage samples: 50g of cut samples were shaken in 0.5g of L-cysteine and 100mL of EDTA solution (pH 9.5-9.6) for 5 min in a closed glass flask. The extract was then filtered. The bottle and the filter was rinsed with 10 mL of the EDTA solution, and combined into the extracts. 5 mL of 0.41 mol. L⁻¹ tetrabutylammonium hydrogen sulphate and 10g of sodium chloride was added into the extracts while stirring. The pH of the extracts was cautiously adjusted to 7.0 with 2 mol. L⁻¹ hydrochloric acid.

2°. Derivatization:

30 mL of 0.05 M methyl iodide in chloroform-hexane (1:1) was added into the extracts. The mixture was shaken vigorously for 10min in a flask with a magnetic stirring and then filtered. The two phases were separated and an additional 20 mL of the methyl iodide solution was added to the aqueous layer. After the solution was stirred for 5 minutes, the organic phase was separated and added to the first one. The organic extract was allowed to stand for 25 minutes or centrifuged for 5min at 800 rpm. 20 mL of the extracts was taken and 5 mL of 20% 1, 2-ethanediol in chloroform (keeping solution) added.

3°. Analysis

The solvent and the excess of methyl iodide were evaporated off at 30°C in a vacuum controlled rotatory evaporator. The residue was diluted with 1.0 mL of methanol and 20 µL analyzed by HPLC (HPLC Gilson 811c; Column:C18 column 5µ Econosil, 250*4.6mm i.d.;

Mobile phase: acetonitrile-water-methanol 25:65:35; Flow rate:1.0ml/min) using UV detection at 272 nm.

Limit of detection (LOD)

A minimum of seven spiked analyte free samples with concentration ranging from 0.01 to 0.05 mg.kg⁻¹ were prepared. (It is recommended to prepare samples of concentrations between 1 and 5 times the estimated detection limit.) Each sample was processed through the entire analytical method (Extraction, derivatization and HPLC analysis). The standard deviation was calculated and the LOD was determined by:

$$LOD = t_{(n-1, 1-\alpha=0.99)} \times SD$$

$t_{(n-1, \alpha=0.99)} = 3.143$ is the students' t value appropriate for a 99% confidence level and a standard deviation estimate with n-1 degrees of freedom. The t values are given in appendix 6.

SD = standard deviation of the replicate analyses [12]

Recovery of mancozeb from field samples

Recovery tests were done to determine the analytical extraction efficiencies of the methods used to extract mancozeb from tomato and cabbage samples, to put in evidence any loss of the pesticide due to the chain of processes involved in the preparation of samples for analysis.

Tomato and cabbage samples that were pre-analysed and found to have no detectable residues of the targeted compounds were used as blanks. Recovery tests were done for mancozeb. 50g of blank tomato and cabbage cut into smaller pieces each were spiked separately with 0.0625mg, 0.025mg and 0.0125 mg of mancozeb standard. The percentage recoveries were calculated by comparing the concentrations of the fortified extracts to the standard as follows:

$$\text{Recovery (\%)} = \frac{\text{Amount recovered}}{\text{Amount spiked}} \times 100$$

The amount recovered was got according to the equation from the calibration curve (Concentration versus absorbance: Lambert Beer's Law):

$$\text{Absorbance} = 74.36\text{Concentration} - 2.7566. (Y = aX + b)$$

Recoveries between 70 - 120% were accepted without correction, but for recoveries out of this range it was necessary to correct the results for recovery. The corrected concentration is given by:

$$Y = \frac{\text{Concentration} \times 100}{\text{Recovery percentage}}$$

Y = the corrected or expected concentration

Data analysis

Each analysis was repeated 3 times on triplicate extracts so that each result would be an average of 3 data [13]. Statistical analysis was computed on the software STATVIEW. Complete Descriptive Statistics were calculated for the concentration. Analysis of Variance (Fisher's ANOVA) was used to compare concentrations between sites. As means of data were tested for normality using the coefficient of variance (CV = 54.6 %) the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was equally used as a non parametric test to compare the means. Thus, the grouping of means was done according to the Kolmogorov-Smirnov results. The frequency distribution of concentration classes was also computed. Arithmetic means and standard errors were calculated from positive quantifiable samples only. The different data was compared to International Standards for dithiocarbamates residues in Human and animal food.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Survey of dithiocarbamates use in crops cultivation at Bukavu region

The survey which was conducted in five areas of Bukavu region (Kamanyola, Nyangezi, Katana, Miti and Mudaka) covered 60 farmers. 86.7 % of those knew the Mancozeb pesticide, 81.7 % recognised to use Dithanes-45 (Trade name for Mancozeb) to fight against tomato pests. They usually get the pesticide from Veterinary pharmacies and none governmental organisations (NGOs) involved in the promotion of vegetable cultivation. Most of the farmers spray themselves their fields. Only some few resort

to a technician. They confirmed that tomatoes were sprayed the very day or the day before harvest for a good preservation, and this was confirmed by observable white spots on the tomatoes the day of harvest and in the market.

Almost all the farmers have never been trained in how to handle dithiocarbamates. On the other hand, none of them has ever been the subject of any investigation from National Services about pesticides they use and whether they follow recommended regimes in using the pesticides. Nevertheless, few of them acknowledge answering sporadically to some questionnaires from Rural Development and Agriculture students of different university institutions. The fields of 75% of 60 farmers interviewed were targeted for the analysis of dithiocarbamate residues in tomatoes and cabbages.

Identification of Ethylene bis-dithiocarbamate pesticide residues

Analysis of tomato and cabbages samples using the HPLC-UV showed a peak at 5 minutes for positive tests. The retention time of 5 minutes for spiked cabbages and tomatoes was found to be the same as that of Mancozeb standards as shown in figures 2,3 and 4 below.

Figure 2: HPLC-UV chromatogram for dithiocarbamate standard

Figure 3: HPLC-UV Chromatogram for a spiked cabbage sample

Figure 4: HPLC-UV Chromatogram for a spiked tomato sample.

Average percentage recoveries

Satisfactory recoveries with the great majority above 70% were obtained from spiked representative cabbages in triplicate at 0.2, 0.4 and 1 mg.kg⁻¹ (Table 1). But for tomato samples all recoveries were below 70%. The mean recoveries of the detected residues varied from 73.5 to 82.1 % for cabbages and from 64.0 to 66.9 % for tomatoes samples at 0.2, 0.4 and 1 mg.kg⁻¹. The best recovery was obtained for the concentrations 0.2 and 0.4 mg kg⁻¹ respectively in cabbages and tomatoes. The great majority of standard deviations were below 10%, reflecting the stability of Ethylene Bis Dithiocarbamates during sample preparation and HPLC analysis. Results of recoveries are given in the table 1 below.

Table 1 : Average percentage recoveries

Matrix	Fortification level mg/kg	N	Recovery (%)			Mean ± SD (%)	Mean for all (%)
Cabbages	1	3	87.1	82.6	75	81.6 ± 5.0	
	0.4	3	67.5	70	83	73.5 ± 6.8	
	0.2	3	92	81.2	73	82.1 ± 7.8	79.1 ± 6.5
Tomatoes	1	3	66.9	67.8	57.5	64.1 ± 4.7	
	0.4	3	69.7	72	59	66.9 ± 5.7	
	0.2	3	54	67	71	64.0 ± 7.3	65 ± 5.9

SD : standard deviation

The results are presented as mean values of triplicate determinations, N = 3, (± standard deviation). The recoveries from tomato samples are close to those obtained by Gustafsson and Fahlgren [2], ranging from 58.7 ± 2.3 to 73.3 ± 2.9 % in different matrices. The recoveries from cabbages were similar to those given in the Codex Alimentarius [10], especially for cabbages (81.2 ± 1.8 %) and Korean Cabbages (85.9 ± 2.6 %). Using a different method consisting in the spectrophotometric determination of the CS₂ released by acidic digestion of the Dithiocarbamates, Blasco and Picó [3], found average recoveries from 33 to 109%, and relative standard deviation between 4 and 21%.

Levels of Mancozeb residues in tomato samples

Table 2 give corrected concentration levels of mancozeb in tomato samples. The results are presented in mg kg⁻¹ and the average, with the standard deviation for each site is given below the different concentrations. Nine samples were analyzed for each site; 86.7 % of all tomato samples showed a Mancozeb residues

content above the limit of detection (LOD) which was of 0.01-0.04 mg kg⁻¹.

Table 2 : Levels of mancozeb in tomato samples

Sampling Point	Corrected Concentration in mg kg ⁻¹				
	Kamanyola	Nyangezi	Katana	Miti	Mudaka
1	0.97	1.67	1.44	3	ND
2	1.23	1.25	3.42	3.57	2.68
3	0.76	1.45	1.84	1.83	1.84
4	1.33	0.79	1.53	1.54	4.65
5	1.02	0.81	3.99	4.06	4.46
6	0.59	1.87	3.81	2.25	3.85
7	0.36	ND	2.71	3.03	4.27
8	ND	ND	1.95	2.89	1.33
9	ND	ND	1.64	2.26	2.89
Mean ± SD	0.89 ± 0.35	1.31 ± 0.44	2.48 ± 1.02	2.71 ± 0.82	3.25 ± 1.25

SD: Standard Deviation ND: Non Detectable

The concentration levels of Mancozeb residues in tomatoes ranged from non detectable to 4.65 mg kg⁻¹ of fresh weight and averaged at 0.89, 1.31, 2.48, 2.71 and 3.25 mg kg⁻¹ respectively in samples from sites Kamanyola, Nyangezi, Katana, Miti and Mudaka respectively. Of the 9 tomato samples from Kamanyola only 2 samples had a concentration below the LOD. Only a third of the tomato samples from Nyangezi showed concentrations below the LOD. All the tomato samples from Katana had Mancozeb residues ranging from 1.44 to 3.99 mg kg⁻¹. Tomato Samples from Miti had Mancozeb residues level ranging from 1.54 to 4.06 and those from Mudaka ranged between 1.33 mg kg⁻¹ and 4.65 mg kg⁻¹. Higher Mancozeb residues (1.00 to 4.65 mg kg⁻¹) were detected in tomato samples from Katana, Miti and Mudaka. Those sites are in a same axis and it can be noted that 87% of tomato samples gave a dithiocarbamate positive test. The presence of Mancozeb in tomatoes is attributed to the use of that pesticide on the crops very close to harvesting, in some cases it can be even a day before harvest. It is easy to find yellowish or white spots on tomatoes in the market resulting from a fresh spray of the pesticide while harvesting.

With regards to the level of concentration of Mancozeb, the samples with the highest contamination were from Mudaka (3.25 ± 1.25 mg.kg⁻¹) followed by Miti (2.71 ± 0.82 mg.kg⁻¹), then Katana with 2.48 ± 1.02 mg.kg⁻¹, Nyangezi 1.31 ± 0.44 mg.kg⁻¹ and Kamanyola 0.89 ± 0.35 mg.kg⁻¹. The highest concentrations of dithiocarbamates for tomato samples were from Mudaka (4.27, 4.46 and 4.65 mg.kg⁻¹) and Miti (4.06 mg.kg⁻¹). With the exception of the mean of concentrations of dithiocarbamates in tomato samples from Nyangezi, it can be noted that the concentrations of dithiocarbamates residues vary with the distance between the sampling point and the laboratory in Bukavu. The higher the distance from the sampling point, the lower the dithiocarbamates residues level in the sample. That can be due to different facts such the time interval between sampling and extraction, the amount of dithiocarbamate sprayed on the field, the time interval between spraying and harvest of vegetables and the way of spraying.

Levels of Mancozeb residues in cabbage samples

Table 3 give corrected concentration levels of mancozeb in cabbage samples.

Sampling Point	Concentration in mg kg ⁻¹				
	Kamanyola	Nyangezi	Katana	Miti	Mudaka
1	0.06	ND	ND	ND	ND
2	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
3	ND	ND	ND	0.05	ND
4	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
5	ND	0.07	ND	ND	ND
6	0.07	ND	ND	ND	0.04
Mean ± SD	0.43 ± 0.004	0.07	-	0.05	0.04

SD: Standard Deviation ND: None Detectable

Most of cabbages samples had none detectable levels of Mancozeb, only 5 samples out of 30 showed traces of mancozeb with amounts ranging from 0.04 to 0.07 mg kg⁻¹. Of the thirty cabbage samples, 83.3 % had no detectable level of mancozeb residues. This can be explained by the fact that in the region, the mancozeb is not directly used for cabbages in general; some traces can be found because some farmers cultivate cabbages and other vegetables side by side with tomatoes, then cabbages get some mancozeb drops while spraying tomatoes. Even if the dithiocarbamate is used directly on cabbages, farmers respect the recommendation, they spray at least 7 days before harvest. Since most recoveries were above 70%, residue levels have not been corrected for recovery.

It can be noticed that the HPLC-UV method is a relatively new method proposed by the Codex Alimentarius [10]. Most of the available data on dithiocarbamate residues in food stuffs, vegetables and water, was generated using methods involving the determination of the amount of CS₂ resulting from the acidic digestion of the Dithiocarbamates. Our results can therefore, be compared with data obtained using different methods.

In fact, Maneb, Ethylenethiourea (ETU), ethylenethiuram monosulfide (ETM), and ethylenediamine (EDA) were measured on crops of beans and tomatoes at 0, 1, 2, 3, 6, 9, and 14 days after treatment with maneb by Newsome *et al.*[14]. The levels of all residues declined with time, beans containing more of each compound than tomatoes. After 14 days tomatoes contained the following amounts (parts per million) of compound: maneb, 10; ETU, 0.07; ETM, 0.03; EDA, 0.05. The content of Maneb is higher than that of Mancozeb we have got in tomato samples.

Analysis of 318 samples from Egyptian markets showed that dithiocarbamates residues were found in 21 of the 318 samples analysed or 6.6% of contamination, and only one sample exceeded the Mancozeb Residues Level (MRL)[15].

Caldas *et al.*, [16] determined the content of Dithiocarbamates residues in Brazilian foods, by analyzing 520 food samples (papaya, banana, apple, strawberry, orange, potato, tomato, rice and dry beans) collected in the local market of the Federal District, Brazil. That work revealed detectable levels (0.10 mg/kg CS₂) in 60.8% of the samples, with the highest levels (up to 3.8 mg/kg) found in strawberry, papaya and banana. Those results are similar to what we have found in tomato samples. No residues were found in rice (polished) and only one dry bean sample had detectable levels of the fungicides. That case can be compared to the results

for cabbage samples in the current study. Pesticide residues were detected in the pulp of banana, papaya (including the seeds) and orange (50–62% of the analyzed samples).

The evaluation of the exposure of the Brazilian population to the dithiocarbamate pesticides done by the same authors showed that the daily intakes at the highest percentiles for the general population reached a maximum of 2.0 $\mu\text{g CS}_2/\text{kg}$ body weight per day. Tomato, rice, apple and lettuce were the commodities which contributed most to the intake. In related studies conducted in Uganda to investigate the post-harvest handling of fresh horticultural crops in selected markets, DithaneM-45 traces were observable in the majority of tomatoes on their surface [17].

Distribution of concentrations among sites

The test of normality, using the coefficient of variance, has given the histogram shown in figure 5.

Figure 5: The distribution of concentration

As shown in the figure 5, the distribution of concentrations is not following the normative law; the Goss curve is not respected. Thus the use of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test as a non parametric test for comparing the means, for grouping and for determination of the frequency distribution of concentration classes is needed.

Figure 6 give the grouping of means according to Kolmogorov-Smirnov.

Figure 6: The Kolmogorov-Smirnov grouping of means

This figure indicates that with regards to concentrations, our sampling sites can be classified into 3 zones, the zone A including Kamanyola and Nyangezi, the zone B including Katana and Miti,

and the zone C with Mudaka having the highest concentration of DTC residues.

Comparison of the detected residues with safety levels

There is no data available on the Mancozeb Residues Levels (MRLs) of mancozeb determined directly as dithiocarbamates in tomatoes and cabbages in the Codex alimentarius. Some MRLs are provided by some country legislations such as USA, EU and UK, but all of them are based on the content CS_2 yielded from the acidic digestion of mancozeb. The Environmental protection agency (EPA) recommends 2.5 mg.kg^{-1} (or ppm) for tomatoes [18], the Food Safety Authority in USA can accept up to 4 ppm as MRLs [19]. European Food Safety Authority fixes the MRLs 0.5 ppm for Cabbages and 3 ppm in tomatoes [20]. The maximum permitted level of dithiocarbamates in Germany for tomatoes is 1 mg.kg^{-1} and for cabbages 2 mg.kg^{-1} [21].

Considering data given above, all samples of cabbages had Mancozeb residues levels lower than that of different standards, but 24,4 % of tomato samples had Mancozeb residues content higher than the MRL (3 ppm) of European Food Safety Authority [20]. Approximately 33.3 % of our tomato samples showed that Mancozeb Residues Levels were higher than the MRLs (2.5 mg.kg^{-1}) set by EPA [18]. 73.3 % of tomatoes samples analysed were not good for consumption with regards to the maximum permitted level for Dithiocarbamates in tomatoes (1 mg.kg^{-1}) in Germany [21].

CONCLUSION

In this study it has been established that Dithiocarbamates are widely used in agricultural practices in Bukavu region and their residues occur mostly in fresh tomatoes from Kamanyola, Nyangezi, Katana, Miti and Mudaka (87% of analysed samples). 24.4 % of tomato samples had Mancozeb residues concentration above the MRLs of European Food Safety Authority, approximately 33.3 % of tomato samples showed Mancozeb Residues Levels above the MRLs set by EPA . 73.3 % of tomato samples analysed were not good for consumption with respect to the maximum permitted level for Dithiocarbamates in tomatoes (1 mg.kg^{-1}) in Germany. 83.3 % of cabbages samples from all sites had no detectable Mancozeb residues levels and the rest had less than 0.1 mg.kg^{-1} . This study must be extended to other regions and other commodities in order to prevent the effect of Mancozeb residues.

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